

Original Research Article

A study of 'P' wave axis in emphysema in elderly

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	International Archives of Integrated Medicine, Vol. 11, Issue 8, August, 2024. Available online at http://iaimjournal.com/ ISSN: 2394-0026 (P) ISSN: 2394-0034 (O)
	Received on: 1-8-2024 Accepted on: 11-8-2024 Source of support: Nil Conflict of interest: None declared. Article is under Creative Common Attribution 4.0 International DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13379476
How to cite this article: Sadhna Sharma, Manisha A. A study of 'P' wave axis in emphysema in elderly. Int. Arch. Integr. Med., 2024; 11(8): 1-7.	

Abstract

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) can affect the Cardiovascular system as secondary effects of the disease. The Electrocardiography is a good investigation for early recognition of any cardiac changes that occurs as a result of secondary effects of COPD. The vertical P-wave axis on ECG is a useful criterion for screening patients with COPD. The correlation between vertical P-wave axis and Emphysema was investigated on a number of controlled series to see if P-axis verticalization as lone criterion can be effectively used to screen emphysema in general population. Correlation between degrees of P-axis verticalization and the severity of the obstructive lung disease was also studied to see if this criterion can be used for gross quantification of the Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). Objective of the study is to study the P wave axis and its correlation with severity of COPD.

Key words

COPD, ECG, P-wave axis.

Introduction

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), which includes Emphysema is a common respiratory condition and is ranked among the top five causes of death in the United States [1].

In India the incidence of Emphysema is 4.4% [2].

The pathogenesis of COPD is studied as to be chronic inflammation throughout the airways, parenchyma, and pulmonary vasculature [3]. Pathologic changes characteristic of COPD

occurs in almost all the respiratory structures. Destruction of the lung parenchyma commonly termed as Emphysema, is defined as "an abnormal permanent enlargement of the air spaces distal to the terminal bronchioles, accompanied by destruction of the alveolar walls" [4, 5].

The etiology of Emphysema has not been fully known, but the overall understanding is that lung inflammation caused by cigarette smoke, environmental pollutants, or bacterial products leads to an imbalance of proteases and antiproteases [6]. Although the Neutrophil is the primary inflammatory cell implicated in emphysema, which releases neutrophil elastase, recent studies have also focused on the macrophage and macrophage-derived proteases. [7]. Apoptosis and oxidative stress also act as amplification mechanisms [6].

Emphysemas are classified into three major subtypes based on the disease distribution within secondary pulmonary lobules mainly centriacinar emphysema, pan acinar emphysema, and distal acinar emphysema [8, 9].

The normal P wave axis on an Electrocardiography is 0-60 degrees. A vertical P wave axis ($> 60^\circ$) in the frontal plane especially in individuals over age 45 years has been considered highly suggestive of Emphysema by many studies. Emphysema is associated with cardiovascular disease and is characterized by specific Electrocardiography (ECG) abnormalities [10]. ECG abnormalities of rhythm, axis, and electrical conduction have been described in patients with Emphysema [11]. The vertical P-wave axis on Electrocardiography (ECG) is a useful criterion for screening and management of Emphysema [12, 13]. A vertical P wave axis ($>60^\circ$) during sinus rhythm can be easily determined by a P wave in lead III greater than the P wave in lead I (bipolar lead set) or a dominantly negative P wave in aVL (unipolar lead set) [14]. The Vertical P-wave axis is defined as $>75^\circ$ in Emphysema [15, 16].

First, patients with Emphysema with a vertical P-wave axis have a worse health status than those without a vertical P-axis. Second, the P-axis predicted the severity of Emphysema. These findings might be clinically relevant because ECG is a non-invasive test, and the P-wave axis measurement is a convenient procedure. Pulmonary function test is the golden standard for diagnosing Emphysema [17]. P-wave axis measurement has some clinical utility when Pulmonary function tests cannot be performed or when the elderly patients do not cooperate during the Pulmonary function tests. A vertical P-wave axis was related to a poor health status and frequent exacerbations. The ECG findings before and after Emphysema exacerbations showed that the verticality of the P-wave axis occurs during exacerbations and improves with recovery [18]. In addition to carrying a high sensitivity for screening of emphysema, the degree of P axis verticalization has also been found to strongly correlate with the severity of emphysema [19, 20, 21].

Aim

- To study 'P' wave axis changes among the Emphysematous patients in Elderly.

Objectives

- To study 'P' wave axis in patients with Emphysema in Elderly.
- To correlate with severity of Emphysema with P wave Axis in ECG.

Materials and methods

Study design: Prospective observational study

Study area: Department of General Medicine, Malla Reddy Institute of Medical Sciences Hyderabad.

Study period: May 2023 to June 2024.

Sample size: 30 cases.

Inclusion criteria

- All patients of either sex
- Above the age of 60 years, diagnosed as Emphysema.

- All patients who give informed consent.

Exclusion criteria

- Age less than 60 years
- Any Rhythm abnormality.
- Any Ventricular hypertrophy.
- Any Congenital or Acquired heart disease.
- Chronic lung disease, other than Emphysema.
- All patients who refused to give consent.

Methodology

The Institutional Ethics Committee approval was taken. An informed consent of the patient was taken. This was a prospective observational study. The study has been undertaken in the Department of General Medicine, MRIMS.

A detailed history was taken from the patient. History included the patient's name, age, gender, occupation, and address, chief complaints with duration of the illness. Past history of Smoking (Active and Passive), Recurrent respiratory tract infections, Occupational dust exposures were taken. Family history of Emphysema was taken. A detailed physical examination of all systems with special attention to the Respiratory system was done. All routine investigations along with ECG, Chest X Ray, Sputum analysis, Arterial blood gas analysis (ABG), Pulmonary function tests were done.

Standard 12-lead ECG was performed by trained technicians using a hospital 3 channel ECG machine by TECHNOCARE MEDISYSTEMS (TM-3E) with an ECG calibration was performed at 25 mm/s and 10 mm/mV. The P-wave axis of the ECG was assessed electronically. The vertical P-wave axis is defined as $>75^\circ$ [8, 9].

Diagnostic criteria

The diagnosis was made based on the signs and symptoms and Pulmonary function tests, Chest X ray, ECG (P wave axis more than 60 degrees). Other investigations were done where necessary (Figure – 1, 2).

Figure – 1: Chest Radiograph of a patient with COPD.

Figure – 2: ECG of a patient showing Vertical P wave Axis.

Results

The age of the subjects in the study group ranged from 60-75 years. Maximum number of patients (53.3%) was between the age group 71-75 years. Among subjects in the study group 25 were males and 5 were females (**Table - 1, 2**). Distribution of the study population based on GOLD grade was as per **Table - 3**. Among the subjects in this group, vertical P wave axis was present in 19 patients (**Table - 4**).

Table - 1: Distribution of the study groups based on age.

Age group (Years)	Frequency	Percentage
60-65	2	6.6%
66-70	12	40%
71-75	16	53.3%
Total	30	100%

Table - 2: Distribution of the study population based on gender.

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	25	83.33%
Female	5	16.66%
Total	30	100%

Table - 3: Distribution of the study population based on GOLD grade.

Severity	Frequency	Percentage
Mild	15	50%
Moderate	11	36.66%
Severe	4	13.33%
Total	60	100%

Table - 4: Distribution of the study population based on Vertical P wave in ECG.

Vertical P wave	Frequency	Percentage
Present	19	63.33%
Absent	11	36.66%

Discussion

Amongst the 30 patients studied, the age group varied from 60-75 years. 16 patients (53.3%) in the age group 71-75 years and 12 patients (40%) are in the age group 66-70 years. Therefore 50% of the patients are above 71 years of age that is,

elderly age group are commonly affected. This finding is consistent with previous studies. In the present study, out of 30 patients, 25 (83.33%) are male and 5 (16.66%) are female, the ratio being 5:1 There is a male preponderance in the study.

Table - 5: Distribution of the study population based on ECG changes with severity of COPD.

Severity	Present (n=19)	Absent (n=11)	Total
Mild	7	8	15
Moderate	9	3	12
Severe	3	0	3
Total	19	11	30

In this study, patients with COPD with a vertical P-wave axis had adverse health outcomes and frequent exacerbations than those without a vertical P-axis. Second, the vertical P-axis predicted the severity and the frequency of exacerbations of COPD. Pulmonary function test is the golden standard for diagnosing COPD [17]. P-wave axis measurement is a beneficial clinical aid when lung function tests cannot be performed or when patients such as the elderly do not cooperate while performing the lung function test.

We first demonstrated that having a vertical P-wave axis was related to a poor health status and frequent exacerbations. These results imply that the determining factor of the P-wave axis was the positional change of the heart caused by emphysematous lung hyperinflation, but not by the abnormality of cardiac function. The mechanism for the P-wave axis verticalization in lung hyperinflation is that the right atrium is firmly attached to the diaphragm by a dense pericardial ligament around the IVC [22]. With progressive flattening of the diaphragm, the right atrium is distorted and displaced inferiorly, causing a significant rightward deviation (verticalization) of the P-wave axis [23].

In our study, the P-wave axis was not associated with any cardiac conditions like left heart failure, pulmonary hypertension, or congestive heart

failure on echocardiography, but was associated with the severity of emphysema and COPD. A previous report that compared the ECG findings before and after COPD exacerbations showed that the verticality of the P-wave axis occurs during exacerbations and improves with recovery [24].

In addition, there were no differences in the echocardiographic findings and the serum BNP levels between patients with and without a vertical P-wave axis. In addition, our study further suggests that the P-wave axis predicts the degree of airflow obstruction and future exacerbations more precisely. The superiority of the P-wave axis maybe explained since the P-wave axis reflects the right atrium displacement by lung hyperinflation more directly than the QRS axis.

P wave axis has also had significant positive correlations with stages of COPD, which means that the P wave axis increases with increasing stages of COPD. Authors noted that a greater number of emphysema patients had severe form of COPD and the P axis was more than 70 degrees. Chhabra L, et al. also reported similar findings [15]. Echocardiography may not be readily used in the day-to-day clinical practice. Severity of COPD may be underestimated by cardiologist due to tricuspid regurgitation absence and hypertrophy of the right ventricle. Transthoracic echocardiography may also not be of much use. Air trapping may lead to inappropriate findings of the echocardiography. Thus, ECG has been considered as a good screening tool for the severity of the COPD [25-27].

Conclusion

In conclusion, ECG is a simple, yet effective tool in detecting the patients of COPD who may have severe and future exacerbations, as it gives the information regarding P wave axis. And patients with P wave axis >60 degrees, have severe outcome in the course of the disease as proven in this study.

Thus, patients can be screened and adequate measurements taken be taken for immediate treatment and preventing further exacerbations. It can also be used in remote places where PFT is not available. It is a non-invasive test which aids in easy detection of the patients with emphysema who may land up into severe and frequent exacerbations.

As cardiovascular events are a leading cause of COPD- related mortality, every patient of COPD, should undergo ECG monitoring for early diagnosis and ensuring prompt treatment and better prognosis.

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